

SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF VOICES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Abstract: The way languages express actions and their participants, known as voice, reveals fascinating insights into their grammatical structures and how they influence meaning and communication. This article focuses on exploring the similarities and differences between the voice systems in English and Uzbek, two languages with distinct linguistic backgrounds.

Key words: active voice, passive voice, grammar, similarities, differences.

Annotatsiya: Tillarning harakatlarni ifodalash usuli va ularning ishtirokchilari, ya'ni ovoz, ularning grammatik tuzilmalari va ularning ma'no va muloqotga qanday ta'sir qilishlari haqida ajoyib tushunchalarni ochib beradi. Ushbu maqolada asosiy e'tibor bir-biridan farq qiladigan ikki til - ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi ovoz tizimlari o'rtasidagi o'xshashlik va farqlarni o'rganishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: faol ovoz, passiv ovoz, grammatika, o'xshashliklar, farqlar.

Аннотация: Открывает глубокое понимание того, как языки выражают действия и их участников, то есть звук, их грамматические структуры, а также то, как они влияют на смысл и общение. Данная статья посвящена изучению сходств и различий между звуковыми системами двух разных языков – английского и узбекского.

Ключевые слова: активный залог, пассивный залог, грамматика, сходство, различие.

The category of voice refers to several grammatical ways of conveying the relationship between a transitive verb, its subject, and object. The majority of authors of English theoretical grammars appear to identify only two voices in English: active

and passive. Typically, there are two voices in English. However, in the Uzbek language, there are five voices in common: active voice (aniq nisbat), reflexive voice (o'zlik nisbati), mixed voice (birgalik nisbati), derived voice (orttirma nisbat), and passive voice (majhul nisbat)⁷⁸. The most significant distinction here is in the varieties of voice.

Similarities: Both languages primarily utilize the active voice, where the subject performs the action. This reflects a focus on agency and directness in communication.

For example: The examiner asked me three questions-in English. Imtihon oluvchi mendan uchta savol so'radi-in Uzbek version.

And also both languages employ passive voice to emphasize the action or the object receiving the action rather than the actor. Passive voice in both languages is formed using auxiliary verbs – “to be” in English and “bo'lmoq” in Uzbek. However, the frequency of passive voice usage may differ.

For example: Three questions were asked by the examiner-in English. Imtihon oluvchi tomonidan uchta savol so'raldi-In Uzbek

Differences: English uses auxiliary verbs like “be” and “have” to construct passive voice (e.g., “The ball was thrown”), while Uzbek utilizes suffixes attached to the verb itself (e.g., “To'p otildi” – “The ball was thrown”).

Uzbek has a more pronounced use of impersonal passive voice, where the subject is omitted or unclear (e.g., “Uy qurilmoqda” – “The house is being built”). English uses impersonal passive less frequently. Uzbek employs a reflexive voice using the suffix “-gan” for actions performed on oneself (e.g., “U o'zini yuvdi” – “He washed himself”). This reflexive construction is absent in English.

Understanding the similarities and differences in the voice systems of English and Uzbek is crucial for language learners, translators, and linguists alike. This knowledge can inform effective language teaching methodologies, aid in accurate translation between the two languages, and contribute to the broader understanding of cross-linguistic variations in grammatical structures.

In conclusion, while English and Uzbek share fundamental principles of voice expression, they exhibit unique features in their grammatical constructions and the

meanings conveyed through voice. These differences highlight the inherent diversity and richness within languages and underscore the importance of studying language systems in their entirety. This comparative analysis provides valuable insights into the nuances of language structure and the diverse ways in which languages can express the relationship between the subject, verb, and object.

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